

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE DISCHARGE DETERMINATION PROCESS AT LOW-HEAD HYDROPOWER PLANTS

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Abstract

This paper aims to promote a new approach regarding the method of determining the turbine discharge by using the current meter method, also known as the point velocity method. The method provided in the international measurement code CEI 41 [1] as an absolute method for determining the turbine discharge at hydropower plants. Although it is widely used both internationally and in Romania, the method still has components that can be improved. This paper proposes a way to improve and simplify the current meter method by using a mobile integrating frame for the placement of the current meters used in performing the discharge determination tests.

Keywords: discharge, hydropower plants, turbine, optimal efficiency

Introduction

For the implementation of the requirements of the EC directive 2009/28 [2], it is necessary to use efficiently the water reserve of a hydropower facility, in order to obtain a higher quantity of electricity by machining the same volume of water. In order to be able to make an efficient use of the hydro energy, it is necessary to have an optimal framing of the operation of a hydro power plant in the intervals of gross head and electric power, so that the process of energy conversion takes place in the interval of optimal efficiency of the operation characteristics of the hydropower plant.

The operation at any time of the hydropower facilities is characterized by certain values of their characteristic parameters: discharge Q , head H , electric power P , efficiency η etc. The correlation between the values of these parameters within the limits of their range of variation, determined by the type and dimensions of the hydro-unit, is defined graphically by the so-called characteristic curves of the hydropower or of the hydro-unit that equip a hydropower plant.

Among the parameters of a hydropower facility, or of a hydro-unit, the parameter whose measurement poses the most difficult problems is the discharge.

Its measurement requires a complex measurement methodology.

Between the methods provided by the international and national [1,3] measurement codes, the current meter method is one of the most appreciated and accurate methods of measuring the turbine discharge, and the only method recommended by these codes for the determination of the turbine discharge at a low head hydropower plant.

Current status

Water discharge (volumetric water discharge) belongs to the group of a few basic parameters needed to determine the hydraulic performance characteristics of hydraulic turbines and pumps. Discharge always represents the most difficult quantity to measure and accuracy of its measurement is worse and very difficult to estimate in comparison with the specific hydraulic en-

ergy (head) and active power. Despite immense progress in discharge measurement techniques, this part of the hydraulic machine performance tests is often a major challenge, even for experienced test teams.

Conducting the measurements using this method requires not only the appropriate calibration and use of the measuring devices, but also the correct post processing and analysis of the data, including the use of integration techniques.

Also, uncertainty of measurement by the means of the current meters depends on a lot of factors, mainly on: (1) measurement of local velocity using current meters; (2) measurement of a cross-section geometry of flow channel; (3) determining of streamlines (current meters orientation); (4) determining of parameters for velocity function in a boundary layer; (5) the applied method of calculations.

From the author's experience [4], it can be concluded that the last two factors may have very important influence on uncertainty of discharge measurement. The differences can exceed significantly 0.5 % for different approaches of calculations. Particularly it concerns the flows with highly irregular velocity distribution, especially in case of short intakes.

The velocity field integration methods are based on graphical and arithmetic techniques according to the very outdated literature [5]. However, due to big progress in computer technology, graphical and arithmetic techniques have been practically replaced by various numerical schemes. Nowadays, the most popular ones are based on spline techniques [6]. The expected advantages of the spline approach are, among others, the following: (1) increasing the accuracy of calculation in comparison to graphical and arithmetical techniques; (2) easy and fast carrying out the flow rate calculations; (3) easy possibility of applicability to cases with irregular velocity distributions; (4) easy possibility of an immediate visualization of velocity distributions etc.

The most often applied technique calculates the discharge using Classic Cubic Splines. It should be highlighted that this approach may lead sometimes to inconsistent with reality (inaccurate) flow velocity dis-

tributions, especially in highly irregular regions of velocity. It is related to the difficulties to obtain smoothed velocity function that interpolates the areas of strong bending curve as it happens in a boundary layer region.

Mobile system for determining the discharge existing

Fig. 1. Structure the mobile system of the discharge in situ measurement

The mobile system consist of a series of current meters, a modular mobile frame (necessary for the installation of current meters in safe conditions at points with fixed coordinates and their arrangement in the measurement section), a smart data acquisition interface represented by a PLC (automatically programmable), a computing unit featuring a powerful laptop that will allow calculating and displaying in situ on the monitor of the computing unit of interest sizes.

On the monitor of the computing unit, the values of measured magnitudes measured by the current meters and the individual velocity, the calculated discharge and average values in the measurement section, the graph of the velocity distribution in the measurement section, the information shall be stored in the the database (previous measurements, the parameters of the current meters and the turbine / hydro-units where the measurements were made, etc.).The mobile frame used to place the current meters is a modular frame (Figure 2) consisting of several segments and can be adapted for different dimensions of the flow measurement sections. Also, the modular mobile frame can be easily assembled and is easy to transport and handle, it is much easier than a classical hydrometric frame made up of a single component.

Ways to improve the measurement accuracy of the current meter method

To improve the measurement accuracy of the hydrometric mill method, we propose the following solutions:

- The making a mobile system for the determination of the discharge that has in its composition a mobile frame that can change its size according to the geometry of the measuring section. The discharge determination by means of this mobile system can be done either by stationing the mobile frame at different levels

The existing mobile measurement system (Figure 1) used for the determination of the absolute discharge and calibration of the differential pressure taps on the spiral chamber of the hydraulic turbines in the low head hydropower plants is presented in Figure 1

on the vertical of the measuring section, or by continuous sweeping with a constant speed of the entire measuring section. The second variant will be able to offer a much larger number of measurement points which will decrease the measurement error. In addition, it will also be possible to avoid the influences of the disturbances due to the upstream trash rack of the outlet of the – loading room of the hydropower plant;

The placement on the support mobile frame in the current meter of an absolute orientation sensor, sensor that offers the relative position of the frame, in real time, on the 3 axes, being useful for avoiding the accidental "locked" of the whole assembly in stoplogs, during its descent or ascent. This situation occurs frequently in the case of measuring sections with old stoplogs (Figure 3) which have structural defects left from the initial casting of the stoplogs or remnants of concrete iron left in its section. If the measuring set consisting of the frame and the current meter is locked in the stop-logs of the measurement section, the recovery costs are especially high, with the need for a diving team. In addition, this situation may also lead to the unavailability of the group during the recovery intervention. Another special situation (due to this locker situation) may occur if the measurement assembly escapes through the stop-logs of the measurement section, causing significant damages wicket gate to the turbine and in some extreme cases even to the hydraulic turbine.

- The realization of a new turbine discharge measurement system should include a mobile modular frame (Figure 2). This integrating frame must sweep vertically the entire surface of the measurement section and at the same time be able to change the angle between the axis of the current meters and the streamlines of the flow spectrum depending on the vertical depth. This can be achieved by establishing a correlation between

the vertical velocity of the integrating frame and the rotation velocity of the frame on which the current meters are located.

Fig. 2. Mobile system with integrating frame (left) and Example of lowering and rotating mechanism of the integrating frame (right)

Conclusions

The aim of this paper was to improve the methodology for in situ determination of the flow and to increase the accuracy of flow determination by using absolute measurement method of discharge, current meter method.

This paper proposes the implementation of a system mobile determination in situ of discharge what does it use a mobile frame what has a device capable of modifying the angle of location of the current meters depending on the flow spectrum in the measurement section, such that that the angle between the current meter axis and the tangent to the current lines of the flow spectrum to be max. 5° . The use of this device will eliminate the error introduced in the discharge calculation by the angle between the axis of the current meters and the tangent to the current lines of the flow spectrum, error encountered in the discharge measurements performed with the current meters placed on a mobile frame.

The use of the modular mobile frame instead of the fixed frame will reduce the time required to mount the current meter on the frame and reduce the number of current meters used. Also, with the help of the computing program, the discharge will be calculated in situ using one or more calculation methods, which will increase the accuracy of the methodology to determine in situ of the discharge.

Although the mobile frame was designed for to determine the discharge for hydropower plants it's can also be used in other locations (open channels, thermal power plants) and can be modified according to the measurement section. The mobile frame for discharge determination proposed in this paper can be used periodically for the determination of the discharge and calibration of the pressure tape of the from the spiral chamber of the hydraulic turbine in hydropower plants, in order to s a benchmark for other methods discharge measure, such as acoustic transit time method, acoustic scintillation method, Gibson method [7].

A general conclusion of this paper is that the simplification and improvement of the flow rate measurement methodology using the current meter is feasible.

The solutions proposed in this paper are viable and perfectly applicable in the usual practice, resulting in the simplification the methodology for in situ flow determination and lower its cost price.

Acknowledgement

This work was carried out through the Core Program within the National Research Development and Innovation Plan 2022-2027, carried out with the support of MCID, project no. PN 23140103.

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